

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 59

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 59

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 59:0 For the choir director; <i>set to</i> †Al-tashheth. A °Mikhtam of David, ^when Saul sent <i>men</i> and they watched the house in order to kill him.</p>	<p>Psa. 59:1 לְמִנְצַח אֶל-תְּשַׁחֵת לְדָוִד מִכַּתְּמִם בְּשִׁלַּח שָׁאוּל וַיִּשְׁמְרוּ אֶת- הַבַּיִת לְהַמִּיתוֹ: ² הֲצִילָנִי מֵאִיְבֵי</p>
<p>Psa. 59:1 “Deliver me from my enemies, O my God;</p>	<p>אֱלֹהֵי מִמֶּתְקוֹמֵמִי תִשְׁגַּבֵּנִי: ³ הֲצִילָנִי מִפְּעֻלֵי אֹזֶן וּמֵאֲנָשֵׁי דָמִים</p>
<p>^{1b}Set me <i>securely</i> on high away from those who rise up against me.</p>	<p>הוֹשִׁיעֵנִי: ⁴ כִּי הִנֵּה אֲרֹבּוּ לְנַפְשִׁי</p>
<p>² Deliver me from “those who do iniquity</p>	<p>יָגוּרוּ עָלַי עֵזִים לֹא-פִשְׁעֵי וְלֹא- חַטָּאתַי יְהוּה: ⁵ בְּלִי-עֵזֶן יְרוּצוֹן</p>
<p>And save me from ^bmen of bloodshed.</p>	<p>וַיִּכּוֹנְנּוּ עוֹדָה לְקִרְאתִי וּרְאָה: ⁶ וְאַתָּה יְהוּה-אֱלֹהִים אֲצַבְּאוֹת</p>
<p>³ For behold, they “have ¹set an ambush for my ²life;</p>	<p>אֱלֹהֵי יִשְׂרָאֵל הִקִּיצָה לְפָקֶד כָּל- הַגּוֹיִם אֶל-תְּחִן כָּל-בְּגֵדֵי אֹזֶן</p>
<p>³Fierce men ⁴launch an attack against me,</p>	<p>סָלָה: ⁷ יָשׁוּבוּ לָעֶרֶב יַהֲמוּ כַכֶּלֶב</p>
<p>^bNot for my transgression nor for my sin, O LORD,</p>	<p>וַיִּסּוּבּוּ עִיר: ⁸ הִנֵּה אִיִּבִיעוֹן</p>
<p>⁴ For no guilt of <i>mine</i>, they run and set themselves against me.</p>	<p>בְּפִיהֶם תַּרְבוֹת בְּשִׁפְתוֹתֵיהֶם כִּי- מִי שָׁמַע: ⁹ וְאַתָּה יְהוּה תִשְׁחַק-</p>
<p>^bArouse Yourself to ²help me, and see!</p>	<p>לָמוּ תִלְעַג לְכָל-גּוֹיִם: ¹⁰ עֹז</p>
<p>⁵ You, “O LORD God of hosts, the God of Israel,</p>	<p>אֱלֹהֵי אֲשֶׁמְרָה כִּי-אֱלֹהִים מִשְׁגַּבֵּי: ¹¹ אֱלֹהֵי חֲסִדוֹ [חֲסִדֵי] יִקְדָּמֵנִי</p>
<p>Awake to ^{1b}punish all the nations;</p>	<p>אֱלֹהִים יִרְאֵנִי בְּשַׁרְרֵי: ¹² אֶל-</p>
<p>“Do not be gracious to any <i>who are</i> treacherous in iniquity. ²Selah.</p>	<p>תַּהַרְגֵם אַפְּן-יִשְׁכַּחוּ עַמִּי הַנִּיַּעַמוּ בְּחִילָךְ וְהוֹרִידֵמוּ מִגִּבְּוֹ אֲדָנִי: ¹³</p>
<p>⁶ They “return at evening, they howl like a ^bdog,</p>	<p>חַטָּאת-פִּימוּ דְּבַר-שִׁפְתֵימוּ וַיִּלְכְּדוּ בְּגֹאוֹנָם וּמֵאֲלָה וּמִכַּתֵּשׁ</p>
<p>And go around the city.</p>	<p>יִסְפְּרוּ: ¹⁴ כִּלְהָ בַחֲמָה כִּלְהָ</p>
<p>⁷ Behold, they “belch forth with their mouth;</p>	
<p>^bSwords are in their lips, For, <i>they say</i>, “Who hears?”</p>	
<p>⁸ But You, O LORD, “laugh at them;</p>	

You ^bscoff at all the nations.

Psa. 59:9 Because of ¹his ^astrength I will watch for You,

For God is my ^bstronghold.

¹⁰ ¹My God ^ain His lovingkindness will meet me;

God will let me ^blook *triumphantly* upon ²my foes.

¹¹ Do not slay them, ^aor my people will forget;

^{1b}Scatter them by Your power, and bring them down,

O Lord, ^cour shield.

¹² ¹On account of the ^asin of their mouth *and* the words of their lips,

Let them even be ^bcaught in their pride,

And on account of ^ccurse and ²lies which they utter.

¹³ ^{1a}Destroy *them* in wrath, ¹destroy *them* that they may be no more;

That *men* may ^bknow that God ²rules in Jacob

To the ends of the earth. Selah.

¹⁴ They ^areturn at evening, they howl like a dog,

And go around the city.

¹⁵ They ^awander about ¹for food

And ²growl if they are not satisfied.

Psa. 59:16 But as for me, I shall ^asing of Your strength;

Yes, I shall ^bjoyfully sing of Your lovingkindness in the ^cmorning,

For You have been my ^dstronghold

And a ^crefuge in the day of my distress.

¹⁷ ^aO my strength, I will sing praises to You;

וְאֵינָמוּ וַיִּדְעוּ כִּי־אֱלֹהִים מִשָּׁל
בְּיַעֲקֹב לְאַפְסֵי הָאָרֶץ סֵלָה : 15
וַיָּשׁוּבוּ לָעָרִב יַהֲמוּ כַכֶּלֶב וַיִּסּוּבּוּ
עִיר : 16 הֲמָה יְנוּעוּן [יְנִיעוּן]
לֹא־אֵם לֹא־אֶשְׁבְּעוּ וַיִּלְיֵנוּ : 17
וְאֲנִי אֲשִׁיר עֵדָה וְאֶרְנֵן לְבָקָר
חֲסִידָךְ כִּי־תִיַתְּ מִשָּׁגֵב לִי וּמָנוֹס
בַּיּוֹם צָר־לִי : 18 עֲזֵי אֱלֹהֶיךָ אֲזַמְּרָה
כִּי־אֱלֹהִים מִשָּׁגֵבִי אֱלֹהֵי חֲסָדַי :

For God is my ^b stronghold, the ¹ God who shows me lovingkindness.	
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References

Psalm 59:0

[†]Lit *Do Not Destroy*

[°]Possibly *Epigrammatic Poem* or *Atonement Psalm*

[^]1 Sam 19:11

Psalm 59:1

¹Or *May You put me in an inaccessibly high place*

^aPs 143:9

^bPs 20:1; 69:29

Psalm 59:2

^aPs 28:3; 36:12; 53:4; 92:7; 94:16

^bPs 26:9; 139:19; Prov 29:10

Psalm 59:3

¹Or *lain in wait*

²Lit *soul*

³Or *Strong*

⁴Or *stir up strife*

^aPs 56:6

^b1 Sam 24:11; Ps 7:3, 4; 69:4

Psalm 59:4

¹Lit *Without guilt*

²Lit *meet*

^aPs 35:19

^bPs 7:6; 35:23

Psalm 59:5

¹Lit *visit*

²*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

^aPs 69:6; 80:4; 84:8

^bPs 9:5; Is 26:14

^cIs 2:9; Jer 18:23

Psalm 59:6

^aPs 59:14

^bPs 22:16

Psalm 59:7

^aPs 94:4; Prov 15:2, 28

^bPs 57:4; Prov 12:18

¶ Job 22:13; Ps 10:11; 73:11; 94:7

Psalm 59:8

^aPs 37:13; Prov 1:26

^bPs 2:4

Psalm 59:9

¹Many mss and some ancient versions read *My strength*

^aPs 18:17

^bPs 9:9; 62:2

Psalm 59:10

¹Many mss and some ancient versions read *The God of my lovingkindness*

²Lit *those who lie in wait for me*

^aPs 21:3

^bPs 54:7

Psalm 59:11

¹Or *Make them wander*

^aDeut 4:9; 6:12

^bPs 106:27; 144:6; Is 33:3

¶ Ps 84:9

Psalm 59:12

¹Or *The sin of their mouth is the word of their lips,*

²Lit *lying*

^aProv 12:13

^bZeph 3:11

¶ Ps 10:7

Psalm 59:13

¹Lit *Bring to an end*

²Or *is Ruler*

^aPs 104:35

^bPs 83:18

Psalm 59:14

^aPs 59:6

Psalm 59:15

¹Or *to devour*

²Another reading is *tarry all night*

^aJob 15:23

Psalm 59:16

^aPs 21:13

^bPs 101:1

^cPs 5:3; 88:13

^dPs 59:9

^e2 Sam 22:3; Ps 46:1

Psalm 59:17

¹Lit *God of my lovingkindness*

^aPs 59:9

^bPs 59:10

Targum

Psa. 59:1 For praise; concerning the distress when David said, “Do no harm”; composed by David, humble and innocent; when Saul sent and they guarded the house in order to kill him. ² Deliver me from my enemies, O God; from those who rise against me, save me. ³ Deliver me from those who practice deceit, and from murderous men redeem me. ⁴ For behold, they have lain in wait for my soul, the strong gathering against me; not on account of my iniquity, and not on account of my sin, O LORD. ⁵ Before [there are] iniquities, they run and prepare battle; be strong towards me, and see! ⁶ But you, O LORD God Sabaoth, God of Israel, awake to punish all the Gentiles; do not pity any of the deceitful rulers forever. ⁷ They will return at evening, they will raise a tumult like a dog, and they will encircle the city. ⁸ Behold, they will spew forth with their mouth words sharp as swords; with their lips they say, “Let us boast, for who is the one who will hear and punish?” ⁹ But you, O LORD, will laugh at them; you will mock all the Gentiles. ¹⁰ O my strength, for you I will keep watch, for God is my deliverance. ¹¹ God will precede me with my favor, God will show me vengeance on my oppressors. ¹² Do not kill them immediately, lest my people forget; exile them from their houses by your might, and impoverish them from their wealth, our shield, O LORD. ¹³ Because of the sin of their mouth, and the speech of their lips, let them be caught in their arrogance, for they will speak with oaths and lies. ¹⁴ Destroy them in anger, destroy them until they are no more, that they may know that God rules in Jacob to the ends of the earth forever. ¹⁵ And they will return at evening, they will raise a tumult like a dog, and they will encircle the city. ¹⁶ They will wander about to take spoil to eat, and they will not rest until they are full and take lodging. ¹⁷ But I will praise your strength, and I rejoice in your goodness in the morning, for you have been a deliverer to me, and my trust in the day I am distressed. ¹⁸ O my strength, I will give you praise, for God is my deliverance, God is my goodness.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

David was on the rise, gaining ascendancy, while Saul sank into the lowest depths. David played music for Saul to soothe his anguish until one day, Saul got angry and threw a spear at David's head, barely missing him. At that point, David fled the palace. David's wife was Michal, who was Saul's daughter. She favored David over her father and helped David to escape through a side window. As a ruse, Michal placed a lifelike mannequin (probably a teraphim angel) in David's bed. When Saul demanded that David be brought before him, Michal claimed he was ill and could not get out of bed. Saul dispatched messengers, saying, "Bring him back to me in his bed so that I myself can slay him." When the soldiers went with the messengers to collect David, they discovered they were deceived. David was gone.

David composed this Psalm of entreaty and thanksgiving upon his narrow escape from Saul.

The superscript offers the theme of this Psalm. Saul was raging with jealousy. Saul did not want David killed in his own home because his wife was Saul's daughter. That is why Saul demanded that David be brought before him.

To the Sefirah Netzach who offers victory. Let not destruction come. A tenet by David when Saul sent soldiers to watch the house in order to slay him.

Verse one

The real source of danger for the kingdom was Saul. In this Psalm, David only speaks about the men who, instead of appeasing Saul's insane jealousy of David, did everything they could to fan Saul's hostility even more. They became the tools of Saul's plot against David.

Deliver me from my enemies, O God. Set me up on high over those who rise up against me.

Verse two

The soldiers who were trying to carry out Saul's orders were workers of violence.

Deliver me from the workers of violence and save me from blood-thirsty men.

Verses three and four

David said the soldiers looking for him became strong because they worked together for a common goal. They wanted to bring David back to Saul not because of David's sins but of some other situation.

For behold, they lie in wait for my soul, impudently they gather together against me; it is not for my transgressions and not for my sins, O merciful LORD.

It is not because of my faults that they run and prepare themselves; awake to help me and behold.

Verse five

David asked the LORD why men of violence are allowed to exist, especially in Israel

And you, O LORD, God of Hosts, the God of Israel, arouse Yourself to remember all the nations; show not favor to all the faithless men of violence. Meditate on this verse.

Verse six

They return toward evening; they howl like dogs and go around the city.

Verse seven

The men chasing David were open about their intentions. Their words were more deadly than their swords.

Behold, they spew forth everything from their mouths, swords are in their lips, for “Who hears it?”

Verse eight

The LORD sends suffering to innocent men to test and train them. A righteous man will never be allowed to perish. David saw this part of his life as a test and for training that would enable him to become the king of Israel.

However, You are the LORD. You shall laugh at them. You mock all the nations.

Verse nine

David said to the LORD that as long as Saul held onto the monarchy's power, he would wait until it was his turn. This demonstrated David's love and trust in the LORD.

So long as Saul is in power, I will wait. I will trust you, LORD.

Verse ten

David felt that the LORD would reveal the Sefirah Chesed (mercy, love, lovingkindness) to him.

LORD, please allow me to feel the power of the Sefirah Chesed.

Verse eleven

David did not want the people to forget what Saul did against him.

Slay them not, lest my people forget it; stagger them to your might and cast them down from their high places. O our shield, my Master.

Verse twelve

Every word from the violent men constitutes a misuse of the gift of speech. David asked the LORD to let their arrogance bring about their downfall.

The word of their lips is a sinful use of their mouth, so may they become entangled in their pride and tell of perjury and falsehood.

Verse thirteen

God's people are called Jacob and not Israel. This indicates that the Jewish people are not worthy of the name Israel as long as it will not use its God-given power in His service and the cause of justice and truth.

Let them vanish in wrath, let them vanish until they shall be no more, and then one will know unto the ends of the earth that the LORD rules in Jacob. Meditate on this verse.

Verses fourteen and fifteen

In David's day, dogs howled at night while finding food. The men tracking David were howling for revenge.

They return toward evening; they howl like dogs and go around the city.

They cause commotion in order to eat if they have not had their fill at the place where they have lodged for the night.

Verse sixteen

But as for me, I shall sing of Your all-conquering might, and rejoice in Your mercy toward the morning, how You have been my high tower and a refuge on the day on which I was distressed.

Verse seventeen

Once the power shall be mine, I shall sing praises to You, for God is my high tower, the God of my devotion.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

Deliver me from my enemies, O God. Set me up on high over those who rise up against me.

Deliver me from the workers of violence and save me from blood-thirsty men.

For behold, they lie in wait for my soul, impudently they gather together against me; it is not for my transgressions and not for my sins, O merciful LORD.

It is not because of my faults that they run and prepare themselves; awake to help me and behold.

And you, O LORD, God of Hosts, the God of Israel, arouse Yourself to remember all the nations; show not favor to all the faithless men of violence. Meditate on this verse.

They return toward evening; they howl like dogs and go around the city.

Behold, they spew forth everything from their mouths, swords are in their lips, for “Who hears it?”

However, You are the LORD. You shall laugh at them. You mock all the nations.

So long as Saul is in power, I will wait. I will trust you, LORD.

LORD, please allow me to feel the power of the Sefirah Chesed.

Slay them not, lest my people forget it; stagger them to your might and cast them down from their high places. O our shield, my Master.

The word of their lips is a sinful use of their mouth, so may they become entangled in their pride and tell of perjury and falsehood.

Let them vanish in wrath, let them vanish until they shall be no more, and then one will know unto the ends of the earth that the LORD rules in Jacob. Meditate on this verse.

They return toward evening; they howl like dogs and go around the city.

They cause commotion in order to eat if they have not had their fill at the place where they have lodged for the night.

But as for me, I shall sing of Your all-conquering might, and rejoice in Your mercy toward the morning, how You have been my high tower and a refuge on the day on which I was distressed.

Once the power shall be mine, I shall sing praises to You, for God is my high tower, the God of my devotion.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

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Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

